

The Pretexts of Modern “Science”

Abstract

The first pretext of modern “science” is that you are not supposed to talk about personal experience, so I will pointedly ignore that: Years ago, I attempted to publish a paper about the lack of protocols for the acceptance of revolutionary discoveries, or in other words, about how nothing has changed since Thomas Kuhn’s book *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Despite it being described as “interesting”, it was rejected without explanation by journals. Admittedly, it was not written with the highest literary standards in mind, however, that was part of the point, as good science does not have to sound good. Recently, I have been considering rewriting that paper, yet I realized that I have been committing a category error, more precisely an informal fallacy: I assumed that what is today referred to as “science” has anything to do with science. Etymologically, the word science simply means knowledge. Science is generally defined as the systematic search for truth. How does modern “science”, which henceforth shall be referred to as Science™, match the definition of science? “Scientific standards” are undefined. They do not exist, beyond vague mentions of “extant literature”, which automatically exclude anything important. Perhaps even more fundamentally, where is the system for knowledge? What do citation counts, “impact factors”, “h-indexes” and “altmetrics” have to do with knowledge, with truth? These are not marginal details, these are the metrics of Science™. Therefore, while there are a few people who complain about frauds, replication crises, perverse incentives and bad actors, modern self-declared “science” simply does not satisfy the definition of science.

The second pretext of modern Science™ is that “science is not perfect”, “people are not perfect”, or simply “perfection does not exist”, implying the basic standards of science, such as being honest or having integrity, are perfection. They are not. They are the basic standards which must be followed for something to be correctly referred to as scientific. Otherwise, calling it scientific is simply fraudulent. Most would judge this paper as “unhelpful” or

“strategically self-sabotaging” due to being “impossible” to defend publicly, yet what exactly is the “strategy”? Whatever it is, it is clearly not working. How many more self-declared civilizations will have to fall until you accept this is true? The third pretext of modern Science™ is that scientists have to be “realistic” or “pragmatic”. Why is “realism”, “pragmatism” and “maturity” equivalent to having no standards? If you are the kind of person who would just wish me “all the best”, then you are the greatest possible hypocrite, worse than the fraudulent institutions, because they clearly do not know what they are doing. You do know, and choose to hide behind the same excuses. The fourth pretext of modern Science™ is that “the world is complex”. If reality were so complex beyond any absolute statement, then science would be pointless. Invoking “complexity” is not an excuse, it is a self-indictment. Either complexity is tractable, so science has a purpose; or complexity is intractable, so science is performative. The world is not as complex as the excuses people use to avoid understanding it.

Keywords: philosophy of science, epistemology, scientism, informal fallacies, objectivity, axioms, honesty, communication, consensus bias, credentialism

Informal Fallacy

The fifth pretext of modern Science™ is that "science is a method of avoiding bias", while only acknowledging convenient, or what they would call "realistic", biases. The overarching example is authorship bias, the idea that an author is biased toward their own work. To counteract that, editors and especially "peer review" are introduced, however, are editors and "peers" not themselves biased? Why would one assume they are less biased? Could they, individually and/or collectively, be even more biased than a single author? Yet, even more fundamental than that is that informal biases are almost entirely ignored, presumably because most "experts" have not even heard of them. Formal fallacies refer to logic, while informal fallacies refer to language. The textbook example of an informal fallacy is like this:

- Feathers are light.
- What is light cannot be dark.
- Therefore, feathers cannot be dark.

The mistake is obvious, in this case the word has more than one meaning, and the meanings are incorrectly used. Indeed, this simplicity appears to be the reason informal fallacies are ignored. Everyone assumes they are obvious, but they clearly are not always so. Indeed, this whole text is almost exclusively about informal fallacies. Pretending the word "science" describes the modern fraudulent institution of Science™, is an informal fallacy. Pretending that objectivity is the same as not using the first person, I, is an informal fallacy. The statement "the Sun is hot" is obviously not any more objective than the statement "I think the Sun is hot". Pretending that following basic standards is perfection, is an informal fallacy. Pretending that pragmatism equals spinelessness, is an informal fallacy. Pretending the world is complex, is not even an informal fallacy, it is simply a self-indictment, since the whole purpose of an expert is to demystify complexity. They are just so biased that they do not even recognize their self-indictments. Pretending that "science is a method of avoiding bias", while only avoiding convenient bias, is an informal fallacy, as bias is defined as "practical bias". Some of these biases can also be interpreted as formal fallacies, for example the last one mentioned could be also the appeal to convenience fallacy. This is why the first standard of science is honesty. Honesty is required to correctly identify biases as well as anything else. If honesty is unrealistic, then reality is unrealistic.

The sixth pretext of modern Science™ is another informal fallacy: "Science is humble." People here confuse two distinct definitions:

- underestimating yourself; and
- neither underestimating nor overestimating.

To underestimate yourself may be humble, but it is not scientific. To be scientific is to neither underestimate nor overestimate, or in other words, to be precise. The latter definition clearly is not what people mean by "humility", and this is a clear example of an unexamined assumption smuggled into science from religious thinking. Science has nothing to do with humility. "Epistemic humility" has nothing to do with humility in the way people use the term. This is, again, simply an informal fallacy.

Formal Fallacy

Naturally, that is not to say that Science™ does not commit countless formal fallacies too. The seventh pretext of modern Science™ is that science is formal. No, science does not care about formality. Appeal to formality is a formal fallacy. For example, “you are fucking stupid” can be a scientific statement, and statistically it probably is. Furthermore, the pretension that the text is invalidated by the perception that I am “angry”, “arrogant”, “hostile”, “bitter”, “polemical” et cetera, is also an appeal to formality, more precisely a genetic fallacy and an ad hominem. The eighth pretext of modern Science™ is that science is an institution, or that institutions can be scientific. No, scientific thinking is inherently independent. An institution constitutes a shared identity, which not only introduces countless in-group, out-group biases, but it fundamentally introduces the appeal to authority fallacy. Science has no authority in the social sense. Its only authority is reasoning and evidence. As such, a “scientific institution” is an oxymoron. An institution cannot be scientific per definition. Only individual minds can be scientific. Despite these facts, “scientific institutions” lament public distrust as though there were no reasons for distrust, thereby displaying either a profound lack of self-awareness or intentional obtuseness.

The ninth pretext of modern Science™ is that science has anything to do with consensus. Indeed, this can be understood as the formal version of the fifth pretext and informal fallacy. The reason a majority is prioritized over a minority, or an individual, is clearly appeal to consensus, normality or majority. This is not only a formal fallacy, it is humanity’s most fundamental fallacy, the basis of all others. All fallacies are born and persist due to a variation of the thought “if everyone thinks so, there must be something to it”. Human history has repeatedly falsified that claim, yet it persists, even in the “institution” tasked with counteracting it: Science™. The foundation of Science™ is that testing a claim many times, in many places, by many different people, would get one closer to the truth. That would be a fine system, if honesty were acknowledged as prerequisite, which leads us to the tenth pretext of modern Science™: “Science is just a method.” That is just absurd. A tool or method does not require virtues to use. Science has prerequisites. It requires honesty, especially with oneself. It requires open-mindedness, or curiosity. It requires love, as in dedication. Critical thinking is scientific thinking, and it cannot exist without these virtues.

Only self-righteousness can, as “scientists” will demonstrate by stating “this is not how science works”.

“Academia”

Of course, modern science does not only commit fallacies. The eleventh pretext of modern Science™ is that “science is self-correcting”, yet absolutely nothing has changed since Thomas Kuhn’s book, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, was published. That is especially egregious because that book has been described as one of the most influential ever written, at least by journalists (Naughton, 2012), but what did it influence? This is not only the clearest empirical evidence against Science™, as the twelfth pretext of modern Science™ is the undying belief “science is incremental”. Science can be incremental, but it can also be revolutionary. Where are the protocols for revolutionary findings to be acknowledged? They simply do not exist, as described in the other paper which I have now also published as a preprint (Ranete, 2026). This is also the strongest empirical evidence that scientists can be so biased that they do not realize that invoking Kuhn, like invoking “complexity”, is a self-indictment. They sometimes reference Kuhn to excuse institutional inertia (Collins, 1992; Masterman, 1970; Lakatos, 1970), despite the fact that his work is the strongest evidence for it (Kuhn, 1970, chs. IV,V). Indeed, this is indistinguishable from religious apologetics contriving even the most damning evidence against religion into evidence for it. Is there any connection between science and modern “science”? No, except of course the branding.

The thirteenth pretext of modern Science™ is the idea that “people do not care about academia”. This is true, unfortunately, still “academics” fail to notice that they are also people, and they clearly also do not care about academia. Nevertheless, if people recognize that people do not care about academia, then what is the point of it? If people are as “deeply flawed”, as irrational, as they have correctly identified, then how could one reasonably believe that people could conduct science? If humanity is so corrupt, how could any institution, any organization, any human thing, be non-corrupt? Indeed, human language, or at least English, does not even have a clear word for “non-corruption”... What are we even talking about? It is clear that science requires people to actually value truth for it to exist. Otherwise, it can only be performative. If science does not provide a way for people to cease being “deeply flawed”, then science has simply discovered itself to be impossible. “But what

about all the progress?” they ask. “We put people on the Moon.” “We cured diseases.” “We made computers.” Firstly, simply pointing to progress completely ignores the fact that it can occur despite the system, not because of it. Secondly, how much of what is considered “progress”, is actually so? Thirdly, who are “we”? “We” did not do anything. A few people did, which have been, without exception, ignored at best or tortured to death at worst:

- Socrates of Athens – a “Father” of philosophy, executed for “impiety” and “corrupting the young” (University of Cambridge, 2009);
- Hypatia of Alexandria – an ancient philosopher admired for her wisdom, killed by a mob of good and humble Christians due to a false accusation (Watts, 2017);
- Galileo di Vincenzo Bonaiuti de' Galilei – forced to “abjure, curse and detest” his heliocentric “doctrine” and to submit to the authority of the Church (Finocchiaro, 2005);
- Gregor Johann Mendel – “Father” of genetics, ignored for a million years (Obyl, 1966);
- Ignaz Philipp Semmelweis – “Father of Hand Hygiene”, “badly abused”, “died from sepsis caused by open wounds and a dirty straightjacket” (Schreiner, 2020);
- Ludwig Eduard Boltzmann – “Father” of the atom, opposed and marginalized until he committed suicide (Lindley, 2001);
- Thomas Alva Edison – his incandescent lamp which later became the commercial light bulb was initially declared “unworthy of the attention of practical or scientific men” and “a conspicuous failure” (New-York tribune, 1880);
- Nikola Tesla – “Father” of electricity, defunded, marginalized, ridiculed, died impoverished (Bernard, 2013);
- Alexander Fleming – the discoverer of penicillin, was ignored when stating that penicillin should not be abused, resulting in today’s superbacteria (Lobanovska & Pilla, 2017);

- Alan Mathison Turing – a “Father” of modern computing, persecuted for homosexuality (BBC, 2013);

And these are just a few instances. Moreover, it must be noted that there are modern “experts” who unironically argue that the institutions were right in these situations. Of course, it is difficult to show whether it is a majority. It probably is not, because the majority of “experts” cannot be that knowledgeable considering the state of the world and of course of science. Still, the point remains that there exist “experts” who claim that Socrates was “guilty as charged” and argue his death showcases a functioning democracy (University of Cambridge, 2009). There is also literature that simultaneously and explicitly claims that (Lynøe et al., 2025):

- “following the mainstream consensus is often associated with eminence-based dominance or resistance rather than evidence-based knowledge (Bhandari et al. 2004). In this respect, there is no big difference between 1850 and 2024 (Squier 2019; Lynøe et al. 2019)”, and that,
- “however, we suggest that rather than eradicating the Kuhnian normal scientific phase, researchers could at times avoid premature promotion of new controversial theories and to instead apply a pragmatic black box procedure, focusing on the evidence of, e.g., an RCT”.

In other words, the paper states:

- “Science has demonstrably failed to correct itself for 200 years.”
- “Therefore, we recommend doubling down on the mechanisms that caused the failure, but applying them more carefully.”

It sounds like a parody, as it is Science™. Moreover, this paper states that “Semmelweis’ hypothesis was that cadaveric matters and decaying particles were the cause of childbed fever and increased maternal mortality” (Lynøe et al., 2025), despite referencing three other papers from another author who has discovered that “the main reason for the rejection of Semmelweis's theory of the cause of childbed (puerperal) fever was because his proof relied on the post hoc ergo propter hoc fallacy, and not because Joseph Skoda referred only to cadaveric particles as the cause” (Kadar & Croft, 2020). If good faith could have been

assumed, this could have been assumed to be a simple mistake, but the mistake is, as always, convenient as it makes the persecution of Semmelweis sound more reasonable by misidentifying the cause. Considering the continuous, centuries-long rejection of its basic standards, mainstream self-declared scientific publishing can only reasonably be assumed to be conducted in bad faith.

The fourteenth pretext of modern Science™ is that bad faith is difficult, indeed usually impossible, to prove. This is not even technically correct. Bad faith refers to intentional deception:

- The relevant agents know they are violating standards, and choose to do so.

The only other possible explanations are:

- The relevant agents do not know they are violating standards, despite, in this case, explicitly stating that nothing has changed in 200 years, so they must be literally delusional, mentally ill.
- The relevant agents have no idea what they are doing, but they know how to pretend convincingly.

Ultimately, there is no practical difference in consequence. Even if we accepted the premise that the agents of Science™ are mentally ill, bad faith remains possible as mental illness comes in many forms, and not all of them excuse any and all actions. Otherwise, even if we assumed that they are completely incompetent, it is impossible they are not aware of that, unless again they were mentally ill. Bad faith remains the only reasonable explanation for the agents of Science™, as the only other one is that everyone is insane beyond accountability. Blaming the system would again be a self-indictment as the system is the people. As such, blaming the “system”, is another admittance of bad faith. A practice that knows its standards, acknowledges its failure, and continues unchanged is not merely mistaken. It is dishonest by definition.

The fifteenth pretext of modern Science™ is that perspective matters, but as always that is ignored when the perspective is institutionally convenient. What is ignored is at least as important as what is included, but the former is normally undetectable, allowing for infinite benefit of the doubt. I clearly remember finding much more blatant formulations

years ago, proudly declaring Socrates “guilty as charged” and claiming that while Semmelweis’ case was tragic, it was inevitable given his behavior, yet I have not been able to find them again. Failing to find them, however, may be for the better, as they could have easily been dismissed as “extreme” or “non-representative”, even though I am inclined to think the latter was published in the British Medical Journal [BMJ], which is what made it so striking. The former, I do not remember the provenance of beyond a website, but I am inclined to think it was published by some lawyers, naturally. This leads us to the sixteenth pretext of modern Science™, which is that every claim needs a clear, stable citation, but that is of course not true. The reason I reference my memory, beyond making this point, is that I am sure I read that, I am sure I heard such statements about “mavericks” many times, they are consistent with everything else, I simply cannot find them right now. The reason may be that they were conveniently deprioritized or taken down. That does not make them less relevant, and the reason I mention them as precisely as I can, is not to imply “trust me”, but to help potential readers find them, or to help recognizing other such examples. Anyway, “experts” are of course rarely blatant about anything, least of all about their blind institutional loyalty. The difference between the statements:

- “Semmelweis was a tragic case, but he asked for it”, and
- “Semmelweis was a tragic case, but the institutional resistance was a predictable outcome of prevailing epistemic and professional norms”,

is purely cosmetic, not substantive. Both statements soften institutional culpability and pretend the reactions were in any way legitimate, instead of clear evidence of a dysfunctional, or indeed fraudulent, system. Science™ is obviously rarely blatant, instead it makes its self-indictments appear “balanced” and “contextual”, and people simply do not think about it because they do not care. This is precisely why you must care for science to exist.

All of this is not to say their efforts and sacrifices actually mattered. “We” might have put people on the Moon, and what precisely was the point of that? Nothing. “We” cured a few diseases, yes, that is a real achievement, while people around the Earth are getting sicker and sicker, since:

- Over 99% of humanity lives under unsafe levels of air pollution (WHO, 2024).

- Drinkable water is becoming scarcer and scarcer (Boretti & Rosa, 2019).
- Food is becoming less and less nutritious due to pollution and short-term farming practices (Yilmaz & Yilmaz, 2025; Bhardwaj et al., 2024).

These are only a few overarching focus points. “We” made “computers”, which are mostly used for sending cat pictures. Indeed, they are called computers because they are supposed to be good at computing, calculating, but they are not even particularly good at that. Modern computers fail at representing most numbers, and rounding errors are intrinsic, unavoidable and cumulative (Goldberg, 1991). The point is that “we” never did anything. A few scientific minds achieved something, which was completely wasted on people who do not care about truth, and are consequently destroying themselves with the knowledge they assumed they deserve. “Scientific institutions” are per definition incapable of change due to their very structure. “Scientific institutions” have always pretended they actually always agreed after the fact, as people always do.

The seventeenth pretext of modern Science™ is that “modern science is the best system we have”. Modern "scientists" insist on the clear advances, however, considering the sheer number of useless and/or deficient papers, is the truth ratio of "science" actually greater than that of any one major religion? Even if we granted modern Science™ the benefit of the doubt, the predictions already show that, especially due to “AI”-generated content, "science" will soon sink below the accuracy rating of even religious traditions (Richardson et al., 2025; Hahnel, 2025; Cabanac et al., 2021; Thorp, 2023)... Science™ is not only beyond parody. A simple historical fact that is generally ignored when discussing religion is that the Church also conducted studies. The most known example is Galilei’s heliocentric discovery which was made with Church funding and patronage (Finocchiaro, 2005). Yes, he was punished for it, like Semmelweis and Tesla were punished for it. Perhaps the “progress” is meant to be that the latter figures were not at risk of being executed, but that assumes there are no worse fates than death. Yes, most “studies” conducted by the Church were collections of self-congratulatory jargon, precisely the same as in Science™. Humility has already been mentioned as a smuggled principle from religion, but another essential one is credentialism, such as Philosophiæ Doctor [PhD] and Master. Those not only predate Science™, they are incompatible with science as science recognizes no such hierarchy. “Experts” are just so

biased that they do not recognize their self-indictments. There is no distinguishable feature between Science™ and religion.

The eighteenth pretext of modern Science™ is that greater length equals relevance. Size does matter in science: the more concise, the better. In Science™, however, truth is of course reversed: the longer, the better. As such, while I surely could present at least 1000 pretexts, that would itself respect this pretext, and so be contradictory. The reality is that even 1 should have been sufficient. The reality is that 0 should have been necessary. Therefore, the reality is that all known human literature has been useless. The reality is that that includes of course this text. There were so many details I planned to write about, such as “Fraud, Blackmail and the Weaponization of Integrity” (Forensic Scientometrics & McIntosh, 2025), what is supposed to be the difference between opinion and peer review, and how the words genius and demon share the same etymology, further indicating the demonization of real intelligence, yet all these points become redundant once one acknowledges the basis. Indeed, all points, all known literature, become redundant once one acknowledges the basis. This explains why “geniuses” are demonized. “Genius” is simply sanity. Sanity is acknowledgement of reality. If reality is acknowledged, your self-image, and everything you ever thought, beyond most basic physiological facts such as the need for water and food, become clearly delusional. If truth was never humanity’s objective, then its languages’ function cannot be describing reality, except by random chance.

The reality is that, the fact that this text can be reasonably written, is itself proof that writing is pointless. The reality is that *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* has already been published, it has been called “revolutionary” and “influential”, and nothing changed. If that text failed, why could this or any other succeed? The reality is that the nineteenth pretext of modern Science™ is that someone probably already documented your ideas. That originated primarily from the wishful thought that humanity is at “the end of history”. All generations have always thought themselves wiser than the previous ones, but the latest ones have been so delusional as to actually believe they have solved all problems. The reality is that is a self-fulfilling prophecy: All ideas seem documented because new ideas are assumed to be nonsense. The opposite of science is not ignorance. The opposite of science is self-fulfilling prophecy: The opposite of science is limiting yourself as to believe your

assumptions are facts. As such, Science™ is not simply not science. Science™ is diametrically opposed to science.

The reality is that the twentieth pretext of modern Science™ is that “anecdotal evidence is unscientific”. That is a pretext because, like all other biases, it is only applied conveniently. Yes, it is true that the examples given under the thirteenth pretext were anecdotal, but there are at least two essential points to consider:

1. The idea that Science™ does not in fact ignore, at best, or torture to death, at worst, scientific minds is not only also anecdotal, but completely baseless, as all its concepts are informal fallacies. The status quo belief survives not because it is evidenced, but because it is assumed.
2. Of course I cannot provide meta-analyses on the fact that most scientific minds have been persecuted, and on the fact that most modern “scientists” think that is good. If Science™ were that honest, this text would not have been written. Authoritarian regimes demand “official statistics” to prove abuse, which they prevent.

The twenty-first pretext of modern Science™ is that science is disconnected from metaphysics, especially by claiming that “science does not provide objective meaning”. The “experts” presumably realized that the distinctions between “science” and religion were unclear at best, so as a way to further distinguish themselves from religiosity, the concept of metaphysical became so unfashionable that so-called thinkers preferred pretending that axioms are “unproven” then to call them self-evident. This is the pretextual distinction between dogma, religion, and science:

- Axioms are proofs of the most basic kind, rational proofs, because they justify themselves by the impossibility of their negation.
- The distinction between “logic” and “axiom” is pedagogical, not ontological; both express the same structure of necessity.
- Treating them as arbitrary conventions is the pretext that allows modern thought to pretend that reasoning has no foundation.

What they claim is irrelevant. What reasoning and evidence show, is the twenty-second pretext of modern Science™: There is no objective, self-evident, truth. Of course there exists objective, self-evident, truth, as otherwise everything would be incoherent. Without accepting objective truth, a statement like “there is no objective truth” could not even be evaluated because no distinction could be made between sense and nonsense. Everything is not incoherent in nature, only in social structures, because they rejected the very possibility of coherence, of sanity, of objectivity.

“Communication”

The twenty-third pretext of modern Science™ is that this text is not about science, but about philosophy, humanity and/or civilization. Science means knowledge because it is the only known way to know. As such, any discussion about knowledge is automatically a scientific discussion. Distinguishing science from everything else is another pretext that reduces science, the method of knowing, to Science™, a branded social activity with no connection to it, beyond the brand. The twenty-fourth pretext of modern Science™ is that one needs to be brilliant to make any relevant observation. If nothing else, this text disproves that, as everything presented herein is self-evident, if one acknowledges reality. While most people refuse to acknowledge reality, which makes them mentally ill per definition, for if mental illness does not mean failing to acknowledge reality, then it means nothing; I do not believe there are any reasons to think this text is brilliant, unless sanity is defined as brilliance. Again, everything is so simple. The fact that most people might have never heard anything like this, despite it being so obvious, is simply ultimate proof of the twenty-fifth pretext of modern Science™: People ever communicated. No, there is no evidence in human history that humans ever communicated. To communicate means, literally and etymologically, to make something common. There is no evidence that people ever “made something common”. People always sought people with whom they already agreed with, forming information bubbles.

“I would never die for my beliefs because I might be wrong”, is the first commandment of Science™, which hides the problem that “scientists” refuse to do anything for integrity, not just dying. The second commandment of Science™ is: “Extraordinary claims require extraordinary evidence.” But who decides what is “extraordinary”, in either sense?... The third commandment of Science™ is that “science is characterized by

collaboration and cooperation” (Richardson et al., 2025), while presenting how it is increasingly falling apart. Again and again, “scientists” are too biased to recognize their own self-indictments. Science is characterized by alignment with reality, which can look like “collaboration and cooperation” only if the agents are aligned with reality. If the agents are aligned with anything else, then it becomes Science™. “Collaboration and cooperation” are not evidence that communication happened. They are merely the appearance of alignment, either with reality or within an information bubble. It is clear that Science™ is an information bubble of self-righteous cowards, indistinguishable from the clergy they pretend both to replace and not to replace. This is demonstrable as information bubbles interpret descriptions of themselves as attacks by definition, further indicating that communication is impossible, an epiphenomenon of alignment. People have changed their own alignments, never provably anyone else’s.

I have been accused of having an agenda before. It is true: My agenda is alignment with reality. I personally only ever “convinced” people who already agreed with me. Sometimes, people unironically claim that I “changed their lives”, and soon after act as if nothing happened, which admittedly is rather scary. If you think you ever communicated anything, there are two questions that must be asked first:

1. Are you sure they did not already hold that belief, even if not clearly?
2. Are you sure they were not just avoiding conflict?

The reality is that, if one actually thought scientifically, one would immediately realize there is no evidence communication ever happened. The simplest possible explanation, the one with the fewest assumptions, is that only the appearance of communication has been held sacred. The fact that most people would declare this text to be anything than it is, declaring it nihilistic for simply applying scientific standards consistently, is further evidence that communication never happened. The fact that only a few people will accept this text, is further evidence that communication never happened. The fact that some people will claim this is “circular reasoning”, is further evidence that communication never happened.

References

- Bernard, C. W. (2013). *Tesla: Inventor of the Electrical Age*. United States: Princeton University Press.
- Bhardwaj R. L. Parashar A. Parewa H. P. Vyas L. (2024). An Alarming Decline in the Nutritional Quality of Foods: The Biggest Challenge for Future Generations' Health. *Foods*, 13(6): 877. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13060877>
- Boretti, A. & Rosa, L. (2019). Reassessing the projections of the World Water Development Report. *npj Clean Water*, 2(15). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-019-0039-9>
- British Broadcasting Corporation [BBC]. (2013, Dec. 24). Royal pardon for codebreaker Alan Turing. <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-25495315>
- Cabanac, G., Labbé, C., Magazinov, A. (2021). Tortured phrases: A dubious writing style emerging in science. Evidence of critical issues affecting established journals. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.06751>
- Collins, H. (1992). *Changing Order: Replication and Induction in Scientific Practice*. United States: The University of Chicago Press.
- Finocchiaro, M. A. (2005). *Retrying Galileo, 1633–1992*. United States: University of California Press.
- Forensic Scientometrics & McIntosh, L. (2025, Mar. 19). Fraud, Blackmail, and the Weaponization of Integrity. <https://fosci.substack.com/p/fraud-blackmail-and-the-weaponization>
- Goldberg, D. (1991). What every computer scientist should know about floating-point arithmetic. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 23(1), 5-48. <https://doi.org/10.1145/103162.103163>
- Hahnel, M. (2025, July 24). Have we already hit the peer review breaking point? OpenResearch.wtf. <https://www.openresearch.wtf/have-we-already-hit-the-peer-review-breaking-point/>

- Kadar, N. & Croft, R. D. (2020). Why Semmelweis's doctrine was rejected: evidence from the first publication of his results by Friedrich Wiegner, and an editorial commenting on the results. *The British Journal for the History of Science*, 53(3), 389-395.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007087420000229>
- Kuhn, T. S. (1970). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. United States: The University of Chicago Press.
- Lakatos, I. (1970). Falsification and the Methodology of Scientific Research Programmes. In I. Lakatos & A. Musgrave (eds.), *Criticism and the Growth of Knowledge: Proceedings of the International Colloquium in the Philosophy of Science*. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Lindley, D. (2001). *Boltzmann's atom: the great debate that launched a revolution in physics*. United States: Free Press.
- Lobanovska, M. & Pilla, G. (2017). Penicillin's Discovery and Antibiotic Resistance: Lessons for the Future? *Yale J Biol Med.*, 90(1): 135-145.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5369031/>
- Lynøe, N., Juth, N., Eriksson, A. (2025). The disservice of publishing preliminary results based on a premature hypothesis – Semmelweis' ordeal revisited. *Med Health Care and Philos.*, 28, 261-273. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11019-025-10257-8>
- Masterman, M. (1970). The Nature of a Paradigm. In I. Lakatos & A. Musgrave (eds.), *Criticism and the Growth of Knowledge: Proceedings of the International Colloquium in the Philosophy of Science*. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Naughton, J. (2012, Aug. 19). Thomas Kuhn: the man who changed the way the world looked at science. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2012/aug/19/thomas-kuhn-structure-scientific-revolutions>
- New-York tribune. (1880, Jan. 1). Image 4 of New-York tribune (New York [N.Y.]), January 1, 1880. Library of Congress, Washington, DC.
<https://www.loc.gov/resource/sn83030214/1880-01-01/ed-1/?sp=4>

- Olby, R. C. (1966). *Origins of Mendelism*. United States: Schocken Books.
- Ranete, A. (2026). How to Publicize a Revolutionary Discovery? Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18115994>
- Richardson, R. A. K., Hong, S. S., Byrne, J. A., Stoeger, T., Amaral, L. A. (2025). The entities enabling scientific fraud at scale are large, resilient, and growing rapidly. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.*, 122(32): e2420092122.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2420092122>
- Schreiner, S. (2020). Ignaz Semmelweis: a victim of harassment? *Wien Med Wochenschr.*, 170(11): 293-302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10354-020-00738-1>
- Thorp, H. H. (2023). ChatGPT is fun, but not an author. *Science*, 379(6630), 313.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adg7879>
- University of Cambridge. (2009, June 8). Socrates was guilty as charged.
<https://www.cam.ac.uk/news/socrates-was-guilty-as-charged>
- Watts, E. J. (2017). *Hypatia: The Life and Legend of an Ancient Philosopher*. United States: Oxford University Press.
- World Health Organization [WHO]. (2024, Oct. 24). Ambient (outdoor) air pollution. WHO.
<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ambient-%28outdoor%29-air-quality-and-health>
- Yilmaz H. & Yilmaz A. (2025). Hidden Hunger in the Age of Abundance: The Nutritional Pitfalls of Modern Staple Crops. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 13(2):e4610.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.4610>